

TOXOSOURCES fresh produce trade and distribution chain in the EEA

Introduction

TOXOSOURCES (*Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified; <https://onehealthjrp.eu/jrp-toxosources/>) is a Joint Research Project within the H2020 One Health European Joint Programme. This activity has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 773830. TOXOSOURCES aims to address the research question – What are the relative contributions of the different sources of *T. gondii* infection? – following the research needs identified by the European stakeholders, ECDC and EFSA. TOXOSOURCES is a strong consortium with altogether 20 EJP-partners, and ready-to-eat (RTE) production is represented in its Interest Group. *Toxoplasma gondii* is a [highly prioritized](#) zoonotic foodborne parasites but is so far not systematically controlled in Europe and globally. Consumption of fresh produce is one of the possible routes of *T. gondii* transmission to humans which has been little explored to date. Thus, in this context it is timely to investigate the presence of *T. gondii* in fresh produce.

As part of TOXOSOURCES work packages 2 and 3, we are conducting a survey on the trade and consumption of fresh produce/vegetables within the European Economic Area. We will use the results to evaluate the possible role of fresh produce as a source of *T. gondii* infection (quantitative microbiological risk assessment), and to design a sampling strategy for a multi-centre study investigating fresh produce for presence of *T. gondii* oocysts.

We would be very grateful for your help with this study. Firstly, we would ask you to

complete this online questionnaire survey. Secondly, we offer the opportunity to test your products for *T. gondii*. Thus, your company will be among the first companies to get their products tested, for free and by top specialists. The online questionnaire has been designed to collect information to identify the most frequently sold fresh produce (particularly fourth range products) in each country and obtain some information on the processing measures/steps that may influence the safety of the final product.

Your company name and the origin of the data will be kept entirely confidential. Collected data will be used for research purposes only within the TOXOSOURCES project and will be not disclosed to third parties. We will ensure secure and confidential storage of data.

Those companies willing to participate will have access to the online summary of the results obtained that will be available via the TOXOSOURCES project page.

Please do not hesitate to get in touch with us (gemaga@ucm.es; r.calero@ucm.es; m.betson@surrey.ac.uk) if you have any questions. We would be very grateful if you could complete the questionnaire by 28th February 2021.

Many thanks for your participation in this study.

WP3-T2 Task Leader

Rafael Calero; Complutense University of Madrid, School of Veterinary Medicine (Madrid, Spain)

WP3-T2 Deputy Task Leader

Martha Betson; University of Surrey, School of Veterinary Medicine (Guildford, United Kingdom)

WP3-T2 Task participant

Gema Álvarez-García; Complutense University of Madrid, School of Veterinary Medicine (Madrid, Spain)

WP3 Leader

Marco Lalle; Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Department of Infectious Diseases, Unit of Foodborne and Neglected Parasitic Diseases, European Union Reference Laboratory for Parasites (Rome, Italy)

WP2 Leader

Marieke Opsteegh; National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM),
Centre for Infectious Disease Control (Bilthoven, the Netherlands)

TOXOSOURCES Project Leader

Pikka Jokelainen; Statens Serum Institut (SSI) (Copenhagen, Denmark)

TOXOSOURCES Project co-leader

Joke van der Giessen; National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM),
Centre for Infectious Disease Control (Bilthoven, the Netherlands)

Privacy notice

We will be collecting and using some personal data (contact name and email address) in this study. This information will be used to request samples for *Toxoplasma* testing.

The University of Surrey, who has the legal responsibility for managing the personal data in this study, will act as the 'Data Controller' for this study. The research team will process your personal data on behalf of the controller and are responsible for looking after your information and using it properly.

As a publicly-funded organisation, we have to ensure that when we use **identifiable personal** information from people who have agreed to take part in research, that this data is processed fairly and lawfully. The University of Surrey processes personal data for the purposes of carrying out research in the **public interest**. This means that we will use and look after any personal data in the ways needed to achieve the outcomes of the study.

Personal data will be held and processed in the strictest confidence, and in accordance with current data protection regulations. When acting as the data controller, the University will keep identifiable information for 1 year after the study has finished after which time any identifiers will be removed from the aggregated research data. If you would like your personal data to be removed from our study before this time, please contact m.betson@surrey.ac.uk.

If you wish to make a complaint about how we have handled your personal data, you can contact our Data Protection Officer Suzie Mereweather who will investigate the matter (dataprotection@surrey.ac.uk). If you are not satisfied with our response or believe we

are processing your personal data in a way that is not lawful, you can complain to the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) (<https://ico.org.uk/>).

You can find out more about how we use your information <https://www.surrey.ac.uk/information-management/data-protection> and/or by contacting dataprotection@surrey.ac.uk.

Company summary and Survey participation

The following questions will be used to characterize companies that have answered the survey. No confidential information, such as company name, will be published or shared with third parties.

What is your company name? *Optional*

Where is your company located?

What is your company size (number of workers)?

Would your company be able to provide samples from fresh produce to be tested for *Toxoplasma* contamination during a study to be conducted in the EEA? A multicentre pilot study, spanning all four European regions is planned as part of Work Package 3.
Optional

- YES
- NO

Please provide additional contact information (name and email address) so RTE samples can be requested.

Foodborne pathogen concerns

Could you list the most important foodborne pathogens (bacteria, viruses or parasites)?

Which of the foodborne pathogens you listed could be present in fresh produce?

Has your company considered any of the pathogens you listed as potential hazards?

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable

If yes, please list the pathogens here.

Has your company implemented measures to prevent the presence of these pathogens in fresh produce?

- Yes
- No

Not applicable

If yes, indicate which ones.

Has your company identified any particular methods or information needed to prevent the presence of these pathogens in fresh produce?

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable

If yes, please indicate the pathogen and the need identified for your company (eg. diagnostic method, product treatment, information).

Questions about production/distribution.

Please complete the following tables about which fresh produce your company distributes in the European Economic Area. Disregard the products that your company does not deal with.

For each product your company distributes/produces, please indicate the countries where it is distributed, the number of tons per year and whether it covers the whole country or only part. Examples: "Spain, 20 tons, total; Croatia, 10 tons, partial".

	Information (Country, tons per year, Area)
ARUGULA/ROCKET	
FAMILY BRASSICACEAE: KALE, CABBAGE, CHINESE CABBAGE, GREEN COLLARDS	
CHARD	
CHICORY/ ESCAROLE	
ENDIVE	
LETTUCE: ROMAINE/ LEAF RED or GREEN LETTUCE	
SPINACH	

LAND/WATERCRESS	
ARUGULA & LETTUCE	
ARUGULA & SPINACH	
ARUGULA & WATERCRESS and/or CHARD	
LETTUCE & BRASSICA	
LETTUCE & CHICORY	
SPINACH & BRASSICA and/or CHARD	
OTHERS (eg. lamb's lettuce)	

For each product your company distributes/produces, please indicate the countries where it is produced, seasonality of production and distribution (whole year or season, e.g. April-October) and other data related to production, such as organic or conventional, soil or soil-less cultivation, and protected or open field cropping. Examples: "Belgium, season: Apr-Oct, open field, organic, soil".

	Information (Country, seasonality, production system details)
ARUGULA/ROCKET	
FAMILY BRASSICACEAE: KALE, CABBAGE, CHINESE CABBAGE, GREEN COLLARDS	
CHARD	
CHICORY/ ESCAROLE	
ENDIVE	
LETTUCE: ROMAINE/ LEAF RED or GREEN LETTUCE	
SPINACH	
LAND/WATERCRESS	
ARUGULA & LETTUCE	
ARUGULA & SPINACH	

ARUGULA & WATERCRESS and/or CHARD	
LETTUCE & BRASSICA	
LETTUCE & CHICORY	
SPINACH & BRASSICA and/or CHARD	
OTHERS (eg. lamb's lettuce)	

Fresh produce consumption in the EEA

Could you provide have any data on the number of tons of fresh produce consumed per year in different countries? * *Required*

YES

NO

Fresh produce consumption in the EEA

For each product, please provide information regarding the consumption per year for each country. Please use the following format: Country/tons per year.

	Information (Country/tons per year)
ARUGULA/ROCKET	
FAMILY BRASSICACEAE: KALE, CABBAGE, CHINESE CABBAGE, GREEN COLLARDS	
CHARD	
CHICORY/ ESCAROLE	
ENDIVE	
LETTUCE: ROMAINE/ LEAF RED or GREEN LETTUCE	
SPINACH	
LAND/WATERCRESS	

ARUGULA & LETTUCE	
ARUGULA & SPINACH	
ARUGULA & WATERCRESS and/or CHARD	
LETTUCE & BRASSICA	
LETTUCE & CHICORY	
SPINACH & BRASSICA and/or CHARD	
OTHERS (eg. lamb's lettuce)	

Fresh produce imports into the EEA

Could you provide any data on raw leafy green ingredients from third countries for sale within the EEA? * *Required*

YES

NO

RTE imports in the EEA

For each product, provide information regarding the country of origin and tons per year. Please use the following format: Country/tons per year.

	Information (Country/tons per year)
ARUGULA/ROCKET	
FAMILY BRASSICACEAE: KALE, CABBAGE, CHINESE CABBAGE, GREEN COLLARDS	
CHARD	
CHICORY/ ESCAROLE	
ENDIVE	
LETTUCE: ROMAINE/ LEAF RED or GREEN LETTUCE	
SPINACH	
LAND/WATERCRESS	

ARUGULA & LETTUCE	
ARUGULA & SPINACH	
ARUGULA & WATERCRESS and/or CHARD	
LETTUCE & BRASSICA	
LETTUCE & CHICORY	
SPINACH & BRASSICA and/or CHARD	
OTHERS (eg. lamb's lettuce)	

Questionnaire completion

You have now completed the questionnaire.

Final page

Thank you very much for completing this questionnaire. We are very grateful for your valuable contribution to TOXOSOURCES.

WP3-T2 Task Leader

Rafael Calero; Complutense University of Madrid, School of Veterinary Medicine (Madrid, Spain); r.calero@ucm.es

WP3-T2 Deputy Task Leader

Martha Betson; University of Surrey, School of Veterinary Medicine (Guildford, United Kingdom); m.betson@surrey.ac.uk

WP3-T2 Task participant

Gema Álvarez-García; Complutense University of Madrid, School of Veterinary Medicine (Madrid, Spain); gemaga@ucm.es

WP3 Leader

Marco Lalle; Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Department of Infectious Diseases, Unit of Foodborne and Neglected Parasitic Diseases, European Union Reference Laboratory for Parasites (Rome, Italy)

WP2 Leader

Marieke Opsteegh; National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), Centre for Infectious Disease Control (Bilthoven, the Netherlands)

TOXOSOURCES Project Leader

Pikka Jokelainen; Statens Serum Institut (SSI) (Copenhagen, Denmark)

TOXOSOURCES Project co-leader

Joke van der Giessen; National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), Centre for Infectious Disease Control (Bilthoven, the Netherlands)

